

Cluster of MPSoCs, PyMACS as ReOS.

The Problem

Scalable cluster of PSoCs using the PyMACS browser OS with python for FPGAs layer for a ReOS or reconfigurable OS with the RISC V ISA. We define a formal lambda definition of VHDL in a configuration cache and a real time OS for parallel clustering with both coarse grain and fine grain parallelism defined in a lambda framework implemented in python.

The Project Plan

The Project Plan follows the training course on Ultra 96, on petalinux, with the PyMACS browser OS on the petalinux application layer.

Here is a high-level project plan for installing PetaLinux on one or more Ultra96 boards and generating a Python script to program the onboard FPGAs using a configuration cache for implementing a ReOS from instruction level caching and a map to VHDL for a RISC-V target architecture, extended to support parallel threading:

1. Define the project scope and objectives: The first step is to define the scope and objectives of the project. This includes identifying the number of Ultra96 boards to be used, the RISC-V target architecture to be implemented, and the specific requirements of the ReOS system.
2. Set up the development environment: Install the necessary development tools, including PetaLinux and Vivado Design Suite, on the development machine. Also, ensure that the Ultra96 boards are connected to the development machine and are accessible.
3. Create a PetaLinux project: Create a new PetaLinux project for the Ultra96 boards and configure it according to the requirements of the ReOS system.
4. Build the Linux image: Use the PetaLinux tools to build the Linux image for the Ultra96 boards. This involves selecting the necessary components and features, configuring the kernel, and building the root filesystem.
5. Generate the VHDL implementation: Use the RISC-V target architecture library and the mapping tool to generate the VHDL implementation of the ReOS system. This includes mapping the RISC-V instructions to the FPGA logic, creating the instruction-level cache, and setting up the necessary hardware interfaces.
6. Develop the Python script: Develop a Python script that uses the configuration cache to program the FPGA with the VHDL implementation of the ReOS system. The script should support parallel threading to improve performance.

7. Test and validate the ReOS system: Test the ReOS system on the Ultra96 boards to ensure that it meets the requirements and performs as expected. Use various benchmarking tools to measure performance and identify any issues.
8. Document and deploy the ReOS system: Create detailed documentation of the ReOS system, including the installation and configuration procedures. Deploy the system on the Ultra96 boards and provide support to users as necessary.

The project plan outlined above is a general guideline, and you may need to adjust it based on the specific requirements of your project. Additionally, you may want to consider using project management tools and methodologies, such as Agile or Scrum, to ensure that the project stays on track and is completed within the desired timeframe.

Research

Reconfigurable operating systems (OS) are a type of OS that can adapt to different hardware configurations, including FPGAs, in real-time. These systems allow for dynamic reconfiguration of the hardware resources, enabling fine-grain parallelism and efficient resource utilization. The use of FPGAs in reconfigurable OS has gained significant attention due to their ability to accelerate computations through hardware customization.

RISC-V is an open-source instruction set architecture (ISA) that is gaining popularity due to its customizable design and potential for efficient implementation on FPGAs. Its modular design allows for the customization of the ISA to suit specific application requirements and hardware constraints.

Fine-grain parallelism is a concept that involves breaking down computations into small, independent tasks that can be executed in parallel. This approach enables efficient utilization of resources and can result in significant performance improvements.

Cluster of Ultra96 boards refers to a group of Ultra96 boards that are connected together to form a high-performance computing cluster. The use of FPGA clusters for high-performance computing is becoming increasingly popular due to their ability to accelerate computations through hardware customization.

Comparing FPGA clusters vs traditional clusters is an active area of research. FPGA clusters have shown promise in accelerating certain computations that are not well-suited for traditional clusters. However, the design and implementation of FPGA clusters are more complex and require specialized expertise. Additionally, the cost of FPGA clusters is generally higher than

traditional clusters. Therefore, the choice between FPGA clusters and traditional clusters depends on the specific requirements of the application and available resources.

System Design

Image: Block diagram

Image: PCB Design

Image: Chassis design

Rack configuration of ultra96 v2 units, by Bing dalle.

Image: Software Design

The WiFi interface to a cluster of Ultra96 v2 units with a 12 volt bus, takes the form of a network wlan, with a browser UI to <https://192.168.2.1>

This url, on the wlan configure each ultra96 board. Coarse grain parallelism, allows for dynamic thread allocation on the wlan based cluster, using pymacs thread scheduling, and pymas on each ultra96 allows for fine grain scheduling on the quad cores and the dynamic risc v isa ReOS.

Material Procurement

Ultra96 V2 board, power supply, USB to Utah and Hart and click.mezzanine kit are provided by element14.

System Build

Image: Electronics build, Mechanical Build, Software programming

Developmental Testing

Image: System electrical testing, System software testing, System mechanical testing

System Application Tests

Image: The system will be used to audit my environment

Documentation & Conclusions

Image: Each of the project plan tasks will include a related blog

System Concept

Credentials

I have participated successfully in several element14 design challenges and complex Road Tests. These projects are referenced to demonstrate how fully I participate in Design Challenges, my level of technical capabilities and the diligence of my blog postings.

Summary & Notes

In summary, reconfigurable operating systems (OS) that can adapt to different hardware configurations, including FPGAs, are gaining attention due to their ability to dynamically reconfigure hardware resources, enabling fine-grain parallelism and efficient resource utilization. RISC-V architectures are becoming increasingly popular due to their customizable design and potential for efficient implementation on FPGAs. Fine-grain parallelism involves breaking down computations into small, independent tasks that can be executed in parallel, resulting in significant performance improvements. The use of clusters of Ultra96 boards is becoming popular in FPGA-based high-performance computing. Comparing FPGA clusters to traditional clusters is an active area of research, with FPGA clusters showing promise in accelerating certain computations not well-suited for traditional clusters, but also requiring specialized expertise and higher costs. Ultimately, the choice between FPGA and traditional clusters depends on specific application requirements and available resources.